

THE ORIGIN, STAGES OF DEVELOPMENT AND TREATMENT OF CHRONIC COLITIS.

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Annotation: The inflammatory process of the colon is called colitis (from the Greek kolon – the large intestine and itis – the inflammatory process). Inflammatory bowel disease is a general term used to designate a group of chronic pathologies when the disease process affects the digestive tract.

Keywords: digestive tract, infectious, ischemic, lymphocytic and collagen
Intestinal colitis is a pathology of the colon and rectum. The disease is accompanied by inflammation or degeneration of the inner shell due to an infectious, ischemic, medicinal lesion. These include the following diseases:

- ulcerative colitis (ulcerative colitis);
- Crohn's disease – terminal ileitis, colitis, ileocolitis;
- microscopic colitis – lymphocytic and collagen;
- pseudomembranous (infectious) colitis;
- radiation (ray) colitis;
- ischemic colitis.

All colitis has the following manifestations: frequent bowel movements, flatulence, diarrhea (sometimes bloody, with mucus), pain in the abdominal region of varying strength and localization.

Intestinal colitis is a chronic disease with microscopic colitis, Crohn's disease, ulcerative colitis. The causes of these diseases are not precisely clarified. The latest research suggests that the basis for the generation and development of intestinal inflammation is a combination of hereditary factors, the state of the intestinal microflora, dysregulation of the immune system and the environment. External circumstances that can trigger the disease include:

- use of antibacterial drugs;
- transferred intestinal infections in childhood and adolescence;
- food quality.

Acute intestinal colitis occurs when it is damaged by a specific infection, for example, salmonellosis, dysentery. In addition, intestinal colitis, occurring in acute form, is the debut of ulcerative inflammation of complex development.

Causes

The causes of the disease are not fully understood. It is believed that it occurs as a result of a genetically determined disturbance of the immune system reaction, due to which immune cells attack the body's own healthy cells, damaging the colon microflora. This is accompanied by inflammation, degenerative changes in

the tissues of the digestive tract due to changes in the function of protecting the inner lining of the intestine.

Symptoms

Symptoms of ulcerative colitis: liquid stool with blood, imaginary urges, continuous pain in the rectum of a different nature – cutting, pulling, burning, and sharp urges to stool. Painful sensations in the abdominal region are less common and most often precede bowel movement. With a deep inflammatory process, the patient loses weight, feverish, weakness occurs.

In 75% of patients with ulcerative colitis of the intestine develops gradually. A person perceives the episodic appearance of blood in the stool as hemorrhoids. Therefore, sick people for a long time do not seek qualified medical assistance from a specialist.

The diagnosis is established after the examination of the intestine with an endoscope. An ultrasound examination (ultrasound) is performed as an additional diagnostic tool.

Treatment

When treating ulcerative colitis, a diet is prescribed, medicines are prescribed, and the patient is given psychological help. If indicated, surgery is performed. Patient management tactics are based on the following indicators: the activity of the inflammatory process, the volume of damage to the colon mucosa, the presence of extraintestinal signs of pathology, the duration of the disease, the results of previous treatment, and the risk of worsening the disease.

Proctitis

Patients with ulcerative proctitis with mild or moderately severe disease are advised to prescribe mesalazine (Salofalk) medication in the form of suppositories, enemas (rectal forms) at a dosage of 1 – 2 g per day. The effectiveness of this drug has been confirmed in 38 scientific studies. Suppositories (suppositories) for proctitis are preferable, since they ensure high saturation of the active substance in the zone of tissue damage. The introduction of drugs twice a day does not affect the outcome of the treatment relative to a single injection.

If the patient does not get better in the period from 10 to 14 days, glucocorticosteroid drugs (GCS) in the rectal form are added to the treatment at a dosage of up to 20 mg. The combination of GCS suppositories with mesalazine is also effective.

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